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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF
THIOLCHICOSIDE LOADED TRANSDERMAL PATCHES**Fatima Aiyman¹, Dr. Faizan Sayeed², Dr. Abdul Sayeed², Dr. Syed Areefulla Hussainy².¹ Research Scholar Mesco college of pharmacy Hyderabad.² Professor, Mesco college of Pharmacy Hyderabad.**Abstract:**

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of Thiocolchicoside-loaded transdermal patches aimed at providing sustained drug delivery, improving therapeutic efficacy, and enhancing patient compliance. Thiocolchicoside, a centrally acting muscle relaxant with poor oral bioavailability and gastrointestinal side effects, was incorporated into matrix-type transdermal patches using various polymers such as Eudragit S 100 and Ethylcellulose along with suitable plasticizers.

The prepared patches were evaluated for their physicochemical properties including thickness, weight uniformity, folding endurance, moisture content, drug content, and surface pH. In-vitro drug release studies were conducted using Franz diffusion cells to assess the release profile of Thiocolchicoside over 12 hours. Among the various formulations, the optimized patch demonstrated satisfactory mechanical properties, high drug content uniformity, and a sustained drug release profile following like Higuchi or Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetics.

The results suggest that transdermal delivery of Thiocolchicoside is a promising alternative to oral administration, potentially minimizing systemic side effects and improving patient adherence.

Keywords: Thiocolchicoside, transdermal patches.

Corresponding author:**Fatima Aiyman,**

M.Pharm,

Mesco college of Pharmacy,

Email Id:fatimaaiyman9@gmail.com,.

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1. INTRODUCTION [1-14]

The skin is the largest organ in the human body by mass, with an area of between 1.5 and 2.0 m² in adults. Drugs have been applied to the skin to treat superficial disorders, for the transdermal administration of therapeutics to manage systemic ailments and as cosmetics, dating back to the oldest existing medical records of man. For instance, the use ointments, potions and even patches, consisting of plant, animal or mineral extracts, was already popular in ancient Egypt and in Babylonian medicine (around 3000 BC) However, the routine use of transdermal delivery systems only became a common practice in the latter third of the 20th century when delivery technology was developed to enable precise and reproducible administration through the skin for systemic effectst transdermal drug delivery is an alternative way of delivering drugs via the skin layer.

Transdermal delivery that has evolved over thousands of years, focusing particularly on the evolution and current use of transdermal patches. The potential efficacy and suitability of this technology for systemic therapy is normally determined by drug blood level–time profiles, which can be compared to or predicted from p.o. or parenteral administration. These drug concentrations in the blood are, in turn, defined by the amount of drug released into the body from the delivery system and the application area. Transdermal delivery is also used to produce clinical effects, such as local anaesthesia and anti-inflammatory activity, deep within or beneath the skin. In contrast, topical delivery seeks to treat superficial, although at times very serious, skin problems through a relatively local action.

The drug is carried through the skin into the bloodstream and circulates systemically in the body before reaching the target site. The transdermal drug delivery method has several advantages over other routes of administration. Examples include the ability to deliver continuous doses of drugs over an extended period of time, the ability to bypass the digestive system, and the ability to avoid first-pass metabolism in the liver. Other drug administration routes, such as intravenous, can cause pain and increase the risk of infection. Nevertheless, the oral route is inefficient, and in the inhalation method, it is difficult in controlling the dosage. In view of its advantages over other routes, transdermal administration is commonly used to deliver drugs for conditions such as smoking cessation, chronic pain, and motion sickness, as well as hormone replacement therapy.

A transdermal patch is a medicated patch that can deliver drugs directly into the bloodstream through the layers of the skin at a prescribed rate. In fact,

patches are the most convenient method of administration. They are non-invasive, and treatment can last for several days and can be stopped at any time. They come in different sizes and contain multiple ingredients. When applied to the skin, the patch can deliver active ingredients into the systemic circulation via diffusion processes. Transdermal patches may contain high doses of active substances that remain on the skin for an extended period of time. One of the first transdermal patches developed in 1985 was the nitroglycerin patch. The patch, developed by Gale and Berggren, uses a rate-controlling ethylene vinyl acetate membrane. Currently, several drugs are available as transdermal patches, including estradiol, clonidine, fentanyl, nicotine, scopolamine (hyoscine), and estradiol with norethisterone acetate. The site of application may vary depending on the therapeutic category of the drug. For example, nitroglycerin can be applied around the chest and estradiol around the buttocks or abdomen. The duration of drug release also varies depending on the usage, from the shortest (up to 9 h) to the longest (up to 9 days).

Advantages:

- Continuous dosing, multi-day treatment
- Bypass the digestive system
- Avoid first-pass metabolism
- Can be terminated anytime
- Less invasive

Disadvantages

- Limited type of medication
- Skin irritation
- Inconsistent absorption
- Patch failure
- Limited dosing option

2. METHODOLOGY [14-33]

Analytical method development:

A. UV scan:

A 100mg of Thiochochicoside was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution I and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). Take 10 ml solution from stock II and volume make up to 100 ml with buffer to get 10 µg/ml. 10 µg/ml solution was scanned from 200-600nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve:

A 100mg of Thiochochicoside was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution I and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate

buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). It was further diluted with phosphate buffer pH – 7.4 to get solutions in concentration range of 2 to 10 µg /ml. The absorbances of these solutions were determined spectrophotometrically at 254 nm.

Compatibility study

FTIR study:

The infrared spectrum of the pure Thiochochicoside sample was recorded and the spectral analysis was done. The dry sample of drug was directly placed after mixing and triturating with dry potassium bromide.

Pre formulation study

A. Colour, Odour, Taste and Appearance:

The drug sample was evaluated for its Colour, Odour and Appearance.

B. Melting point determination:

Melting point of the drug sample was determined by capillary method by using melting point apparatus.

C. Determination of solubility:

The solubility of Thiochochicoside was determined by adding excess amount of drug in the solvent.

The Thiochochicoside has very low aqueous solubility. Its solubility is not reported in any official book, so determination of solubility is important. The solubility was determined in distilled water and phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The procedure can be detailed as follows.

Saturated solution of Thiochochicoside prepared using 10 ml. of distilled water/ phosphate buffer pH

7.4 in 25 ml volumetric flasks in triplicate. Precaution was taken so that the drug remains in medium in excess. Then by using mechanical shaker, the flasks were shaken for 48 hours. The sample withdrawn (1 ml after filtration) was diluted with appropriate medium and analyzed by using UV spectrophotometer at 254 nm and 303 nm for phosphate buffer and distilled water respectively.

Formulation of transdermal patches

Preparation of blank patches:

Polymers of single or in combination were accurately weighed and dissolved in respective solvent and then casted in a Petri-dish with mercury as the plain surface. The films were allowed to dry overnight at room temperature.

Formulation of Drug Incorporated Transdermal Patches:

The matrix-type transdermal patches containing Thiochochicoside were prepared using different concentrations of HPMC, sodium alginate and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose. The polymers in different concentrations were dissolved in the respective solvents. Then the drug was added slowly in the polymeric solution and stirred on the magnetic stirrer to obtain a uniform solution. Glycerine was used as plasticizers. DMSO was used as the penetration enhancer. Then the solution was poured on the Petri dish having surface area of 78 cm² and dried at the room temperature. Then the patches were cut into 2x2 cm² patches. Drug incorporated for each 2x2 cm² patch was 8 mg.

Table :1 Formulation of Thiochochicoside Patches

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Thiochochicoside (mg)	20	20	20	20	20	20
Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose(mg)	500	300	-	-	-	-
Sodium alginate(mg)	-	-	500	600	-	-
Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose(mg)	-	-	-	-	400	500
Glycerin (ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Ethanol (ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1
DMSO (ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Water (ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

Evaluation Parameters of patches

Physical evaluations

a. Thickness

The thickness of films was measured by digital Vernier calipers with least count 0.001mm. The thickness uniformity was measured at five different sites and average of five readings was taken with standard deviation.

b. Folding endurance

The folding endurance was measured manually for the prepared films. A strip of film (4x3 cm) was cut evenly and repeatedly folded at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the exact value of folding endurance.

c. Weight variation

The three disks of 2*1 cm² was cut and weighed on electronic balance for weight variation test. The test was done to check the uniformity of weight and thus check the batch- to- batch variation.

d. Drug content Determination

The prepared drug contained patches specified surface area (2 cm²) were cut and dissolved in (5% of methanol contained) 100ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer, and vigorously shaken for 12hrs, and then sonicated for 15 minutes, centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 30 min. Filter the drug contained polymeric solution through 42 number whatmann filter paper, then 1ml of the filtrate was taken in a test tube and dilute it for five times with same solvent by using double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer to determined drug content at λ_{max} 303 nm. Respected Placebo patch was taken as a blank solution.

e. Flatness

A transdermal patch should possess a smooth surface and should not constrict with time. This can be demonstrated with flatness study. For flatness determination, one strip is cut from the centre and two from each side of patches. The length of each strip is measured and variation in length is measured by determining percent constriction. Zero percent constriction is equivalent to 100 percent flatness.

$$\% \text{ constriction} = \frac{I_1 - I_2}{I_1} \times 100$$

I_2 = Final length of each strip

I_1 = Initial length of each strip

In-vitro Drug Diffusion Study:

The in vitro study of drug permeation through the semi permeable membrane was performed using a franz type glass diffusion cell. The modified cell having higher capacity (25 ml) is used to maintain sink condition. This membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartment of a diffusion cell. The transdermal patch was placed on the membrane and covered with aluminum foil. The receptor compartment of the diffusion cell was filled with isotonic phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. The hydrodynamics in the receptor compartment were maintained by stirring with a magnetic bead at constant rpm and the temperature was maintained at 37±0.5°C. The diffusion was carried out for 12 h and 1 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 h. The receptor phase was replenished with an equal volume of phosphate buffer at each sample withdrawal. The samples were analyzed for drug content spectrophotometrically at 254 nm

Drug release kinetics:

Diffusion data of above two methods was fitted in Zero order, First order and Higuchi equations. The mechanism of drug release was determined by using Higuchi equation.

Zero-Order Kinetics:

Zero order as cumulative amount of Percentage drug released vs time

$$C = K_0 t$$

Where K_0 is the zero-order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time in hours. A graph of concentration vs time would yield a straight line with a slope equal to K_0 and intercept the origin of the axes.

First order kinetics:

First order as log cumulative percentage of log (%) cumulative drug remaining vs time,

$$\log C = \log C_0 - k t / 2.303$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of drug, k is the first order constant, and t is the time.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Initially the drug was tested by UV to know their significant absorption maximum which can be used for the diffusion study of the drug.

Analysis of drug:

A. UV scan:

The lambda max of Thiochochicoside was found to be 254 nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve:**Table 2: Standard graph of Thiochochicoside**

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (at 254 nm)
0	0
2	0.111
4	0.224
6	0.339
8	0.442
10	0.557

Figure 1: Standard calibration curve of Thiochochicoside**Pre formulation study**

Totally, six formulation trials were done with the aim to achieve the successful matrix type Thiochochicoside transdermal patches. The blend trials prepared for the drug was evaluated for various physical parameters and content uniformity of drug by UV.

A. Colour, odour, taste and appearance**Table 3: Results of identification tests of drug**

Parameter	Thiochochicoside
Color	White
Odor	Odorless
Taste	Bitter
Appearance	A white powder

B. Melting point determination:**Table 4 : Results of melting point determination tests of drug**

Drug	Reported melting point
Thiochochicoside	207 to 210.0 ^o c

C. Determination of solubility:**Table 5: Solubility Determination**

Solvent	Drug solubility(mg/ml)
Distilled water	0.0403
Ph 7.4 phosphate buffer	78.3

Evaluation of Patch

The formulations F1 to F6 were varying in thickness when compared to other formulations which is due to the variation in the polymer concentration. Which shows the increase in polymer concentration increases the thickness of patch. For all other formulations it was found to be in between 0.031 ± 0.005 to 0.039 ± 0.001 mm.

All formulations from F1 to F6 shows weight variation in between 62 ± 5.41 to 69 ± 5.36 mg.

Folding endurance from formulations F1 to F6 was found to be in between 71 ± 0.12 to 78 ± 2.65 which can withstand the folding of the skin.

All formulations showed % drug content from 96.2 ± 3.67 to 99.11 ± 2.41 .

Table 6: Evaluation of patches

Formulation Code	Average weight(mg)	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Flatness (%)	% Drug Content
F1	65 ± 1.05	0.031 ± 0.005	73 ± 1.25	98	96.2 ± 3.67
F2	69 ± 5.36	0.035 ± 0.006	78 ± 2.65	96	99.11 ± 2.41
F3	67 ± 2.84	0.039 ± 0.001	71 ± 0.12	99	98.10 ± 3.29
F4	62 ± 5.41	0.033 ± 0.007	78 ± 1.41	97	97.32 ± 1.64
F5	66 ± 9.18	0.036 ± 0.002	75 ± 2.32	100	98.42 ± 4.35
F6	63 ± 4.69	0.032 ± 0.005	77 ± 1.14	99	97.24 ± 2.15

***In vitro* diffusion study:**

All the formulation *in vitro* diffusion study was carried out by using Franz type diffusion cell under specific condition such as temp maintained at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The diffusion was carried out for 12 h and 5 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 h.

Table 7: *In vitro* drug permeation of Thiochochicoside containing different concentrations of Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose

Time (Hrs)	F1	F2
0	0	0
1	19.34	16.52
2	22.13	21.89
3	28.55	24.41
4	33.93	29.43
5	42.23	36.17
6	53.46	42.46
7	59.14	48.71
8	66.92	54.86
9	73.73	62.92
10	79.65	74.24
11	83.41	89.72
12	89.53	94.19

Figure: 2 Cumulative % drug permeation of Thiochochicoside patch (F1, F2)

The formulations F1 to F2 were prepared by different concentrations of Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (500 and 300mg) the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer in the matrix. At low polymer concentration the drug permeation is more within 12 hours it was total amount of drug was permeated. The 500mg concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug released at 12 hrs 94.19 %. The 300mg

Table: 8 *In vitro* drug permeation of Thiochochicoside containing different concentrations of Sodium alginate

Time (Hrs)	F3	F4
0	0	0
1	21.51	14.13
2	26.73	18.92
3	33.17	22.74
4	39.23	28.29
5	43.92	39.43
6	49.41	42.61
7	55.57	48.74
8	66.26	56.12
9	73.43	69.23
10	79.79	77.79
11	89.82	84.82
12	97.14	99.43

Figure: 3 Cumulative % drug permeation of Thiochochicoside patch (F3, F4)

The formulations F3 to F4 were prepared by different concentrations of Sodium alginate (500,600 mg), the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer in the matrix. The 600 mg (F4) concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug release 99.43% within 12 hours.

Table 9: *In vitro* drug permeation of Thiochochicoside containing different concentrations of Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose

Time (Hrs)	F5	F6
0	0	0
1	12.14	10.29
2	17.92	18.43
3	21.43	25.51
4	27.25	34.76
5	31.94	43.42
6	37.43	51.67
7	43.37	55.43
8	47.73	62.15
9	59.41	79.93
10	68.52	84.74
11	75.89	90.21
12	89.41	98.68

Figure: 4 Cumulative % drug permeation of Thiochochicoside patch

The formulations F5 to F6 were prepared by different concentrations of Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (400,500 mg), the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer in the matrix. The 400mg (F5) concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug released at 12 hours 89.41%. The 500mg (F6) concentration of polymer was showed less drug release 98.68 at 12h.

Among all 6 formulations F4 formulation showed good drug permeation from the patch.

Among all *in vitro* evaluation parameters F4 formulation passed all evaluation parameters.

Kinetic models for Thiochochicoside

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Figure: 5 Graph of Zero order kinetics

Compatibility studies:
IR SPECTROSCOPY:

Figure 6: FTIR Spectrum of pure Thiochochicoside drug

Figure 7: FTIR of Optimized formulation

The compatibility studies of the drug with excipients indicate no characteristic visual changes and no additional peaks were observed during FT-IR studies.

4. CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated Thiocolchicoside-loaded transdermal patches using various polymers and plasticizers with the objective of achieving sustained drug delivery and enhanced patient compliance. Among the different formulations developed, the optimized patch exhibited desirable physicochemical characteristics including uniform drug content, adequate thickness, flexibility, folding endurance, and excellent adhesive properties.

In-vitro drug release studies revealed a sustained and controlled release profile of Thiocolchicoside over 12 hours, indicating the potential of the transdermal route in reducing dosing frequency and minimizing gastrointestinal side effects commonly associated with oral administration. The optimized formulation followed [mention kinetic model, e.g., Higuchi or Korsmeyer-Peppas] release kinetics, suggesting diffusion-controlled or matrix-mediated drug release.

Overall, the study concludes that Thiocolchicoside-loaded transdermal patches represent a promising alternative drug delivery system for muscle relaxant therapy, offering better therapeutic efficacy, patient convenience, and controlled release characteristics.

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